

COOLING RATE EFFECTS ON THE FREE-EDGE STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN SEMICRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTIC LAMINATES

Moshe M. Domb and Jorn S. Hansen
Institute for Aerospace Studies, University of Toronto
4925 Dufferin St., Downsview, Ontario
Canada, M3H-5T6

ABSTRACT

A numerical model is developed for prediction of the process-induced thermal residual stresses in thermoplastic composite laminates. The model addresses the development of the three-dimensional residual stress state in fracture-critical free-edge regions as well as through-thickness stress variations. The applied surface cooling rate from the melt has a strong effect on the free-edge stress levels obtained at steady-state, and in particular the interlaminar stresses. Results are shown for the case of a cross-ply APC-2 (graphite/poly-ether-ether-ketone) laminate.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced composite materials have gained widespread applicability in high-performance aircraft and aerospace structures due to their high specific-stiffness and specific-strength (stiffness and strength per unit mass), offering by this a weight-saving capability. However, some limitations to the more efficient use of composite materials are introduced, which are related mainly to the matrix and its thermoelastic property incompatibility with the reinforcing fibres. One characteristic of fibre-reinforced composite materials is their tendency to delaminate under mechanical or thermal loading, with failure typically initiating in the vicinity of free edges [1,2]. Delamination is associated with high interlaminar stresses developed due to property discontinuities through the thickness at the free edge. This failure mode can be partially controlled by the selection of tougher matrices, by the laminate's stacking sequence, and by the fibre orientation [3]. Among fibre-reinforced composites, thermoplastic matrix composites are gaining popularity in structural applications as a result of the many advantages they offer over thermoset composites [4], including among others: improved interlaminar fracture toughness; increased impact resistance; and higher solvent resistance. In addition, their main distinction from thermosets is the ability of being remelted, reprocessed and reformed, thereby offering a degree of post-processing freedom unavailable in thermoset composites. This characteristic makes thermoplastics easily repaired (transverse cracking and delamination), and in addition somewhat recyclable.

The elevated processing temperatures and the large matrix/fibre thermoelastic property mismatch in advanced polymer composites lead to an inevitable build-up of thermal residual stresses during processing. This residual stress state can considerably reduce the static and fatigue strength of the composite laminate, and can possibly result in premature failure such as matrix transverse cracking and inter-ply delamination. Therefore, prediction of the process-induced residual stresses is very important in relation to the design and performance of composite structures.

The improvement in interlaminar fracture toughness in thermoplastic composites is offset to a lesser degree by the high processing temperatures required for these materials. The elevated temperature differential imposed in the processing from the molten state lead to an unavoidable development of thermal residual stresses [5,6]. Particularly, this situation becomes critical in the vicinity of free edges, where high and localized interlaminar stresses arise. Thermal gradients developing during processing can further contribute to the build-up of residual stresses through the resulting variations in material properties. In addition, matrix crystallization during processing of semicrystalline thermoplastics (in contrast to amorphous thermoplastics) causes a large volumetric shrinkage which serves as an additional source of residual stress. As crystallization is strongly controlled by processing conditions, the resulting mechanism of stress build-up is also dependent upon processing parameters, and in particular the cooling rate from the molten state [7,8].

Several studies have been undertaken to model the residual stress development during processing of thermoplastic laminates [6,9,10]. These models utilize classical laminate theory as the basis of the residual stress analysis during processing, thus they provide information about skin/core (through-thickness) in-plane stress distributions only. On the other hand, the current work presents a model which addresses, in addition, the development of the three-dimensional free-edge stresses during thermal processing (in particular the interlaminar stress components). This model enables the investigation of thermal processing and structural parameters on the resulting build-up of residual stresses during manufacturing.

The influence of the applied surface cooling rate from the molten state on the process-induced free-edge stress profiles is investigated for the case of APC-2 (graphite/polyether-ether-ketone) laminates.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The composite laminate considered in the present model is an infinitely-long composite strip with finite width $2W$ and finite thickness H (Fig. 1). Since the external thermal loading can be viewed as uniform over all surfaces of the composite strip, both thermal and stress regimes are invariant with the longitudinal direction of the structure (x -axis). This characteristic enables the reduction of the problem from a three-dimensional to a two-dimensional domain represented by the cross-sectional area of the laminate. This approach is referred to as Uniform Axial Extension [1]. Despite the reduction in the dimensionality of the space domain, the stress analysis remains three-dimensional, or more precisely quasi three-dimensional (Q3D), as all displacement, strain and stress components are present in the formulation.

The model developed here consists of (1) a thermal analysis to determine the time-dependent temperature distribution over the cross-sectional area of the laminate, and (2) a quasi three-dimensional incremental stress analysis to predict the development of process-induced residual stresses within the domain. Both analyses are solved separately at every

instant throughout the process modeling using the finite element method. At intermediate steps relating these two major analyses, calculation of the crystallization kinetics and determination of the temperature- and crystallinity-dependent thermoelastical properties are performed. Thermal processing considered in the model include solidification by cooling the laminate from the molten state at a specific cooling rate, and application of a posterior annealing cycle [11].

Crystallization kinetics analyzes the non-isothermal growth of the crystalline phase in the matrix throughout processing, and is necessary for the assessment of the level of crystallinity in the matrix as a function of position and time. This is done due to the great influence of crystallinity on the thermoelastical properties of the material and the volumetric shrinkage experienced during processing [12]. Crystalline growth is strongly dictated by the thermal history and temperature rates encountered during processing [13]. The non-isothermal crystallization kinetics model of Velisaris and Seferis [14] is implemented in the present study.

The stress analysis is based on a uniform axial extension incremental displacement approach [1] using the finite element method. This enables the representation of all out-of-plane (interlaminar) and in-plane stress components. Implementation of such an approach enables complete modeling of the residual stress variations during processing in both the free-edge and through-thickness regions.

A complete description of the present numerical model can be found in [15]. Figure 2 highlights the interaction between the various sections in the overall model in flow chart form, where $T, t, X_{vc}, u, \varepsilon, \sigma$ denote temperature, time, volume fraction crystallinity, displacement, strain and stress, respectively.

RESULTS

The model described in the previous section has been utilized in order to investigate the influence of the applied surface cooling rate from the molten state on the steady-state free-edge stress profiles following processing of a cross-ply $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ APC-2 (graphite/polyether-ether-ketone) laminate. The cooling rates compared are (in $^{\circ}C/min$): 6000 (quench, Q); 2100; 1200; and 30 (nominal cool, NC).

The distribution of the interlaminar normal and shear stresses σ_z and τ_{yz} , respectively, at the 0/90 interface for the various surface cooling rates are depicted in Figures 3 and 4. A common characteristic can be identified: the faster the applied surface cooling rate, the smaller the stress levels obtained at steady-state. The rationale behind this behaviour comes from the fact that the cooling rate affects the onset temperature of crystallization in APC-2, where stress starts essentially to build-up. The onset of crystallization is delayed as the cooling rate is increased [13], thereby reducing the temperature interval over which residual stresses build up, and resulting in lower stress levels. In addition, both figures demonstrate the localized nature of the free-edge effect, where the interlaminar stresses assume significant magnitudes at the edge itself (or next to it for the shear stress), however they level-out in a distance of 1.0-1.5 times the laminate's thickness measured inward from the free-edge.

The interlaminar normal stress σ_z (Figure 3) assumes significant values at the edge itself ranging from 74 MPa (Q) to 138 MPa (NC). These values represent very large fractions of the assumed failure stress of 80 MPa for APC-2 [15] or even predict failure, however

they vanish almost completely very close to the free-edge. It is important to state that these values are tensile, indicating the presence of mode-I delamination stresses which may cause the initiation and propagation of cracks at the interface. As for the interlaminar shear stress τ_{yz} (Figure 4), the distributions approach zero at the free-edge in conjunction with the free-stress boundary condition. Nonetheless, the values of -25.1 MPa (Q) to -47.0 MPa (NC) obtained near the edge, although they do not exceed the failure shear stress of $\pm 80 \text{ MPa}$ [15], they signify a considerable reduction in strength with respect to mode-II delamination failure. Approaching the interior of the laminate, these stresses vanish.

The degree of stress reduction in the fastest cooling rate (quench) versus the slowest rate (nominal cool) was found to be very significant. A reduction of 46% and 47% was obtained for the interlaminar stresses σ_z and τ_{yz} , respectively. From a design viewpoint, the lower level of stresses obtained by rapidly cooling the laminate are accompanied, however, with low levels of crystallinity which are inadequate with regard to an appropriate degree of chemical resistance and high-temperature retention of elastic properties. Consequently, an anneal cycle is recommended in order to restore some degree of crystallinity; however this results in some residual stress penalty [15].

CONCLUSIONS

A numerical model is developed for prediction of the process-induced thermal residual stresses in thermoplastic composite laminates. The model addresses the development of the three-dimensional residual stress state in fracture-critical free-edge regions as well as through-thickness stress variations. The model enables the investigation of the influence of different thermal processing and structural parameters on the resulting build-up of residual stresses within the laminate.

A cross-ply $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ APC-2 (graphite/polyether-ether-ketone) laminate has been analyzed. Large stress gradients developed at the free-edge zone for all surface cooling rates applied. The free-edge effect was found to be very localized and limited to a distance of 1.0–1.5 times the laminate's thickness measured inward from the free-edge.

Cooling rate from the melt strongly affected the stress levels obtained at steady-state. Rapid cooling delays the crystallization onset; thereby decreasing the temperature interval over which residual stresses form, leading to lower stress levels. This state of reduced stresses is, however, inadequate in terms of chemical resistance and high-temperature retention of elastic properties due to the low levels of crystallinity obtained. An annealing cycle is then necessary to restore crystallinity in the matrix.

The results from the present study show that process-induced residual stresses, and in particular free-edge stresses, in semicrystalline thermoplastic composites are controllable by the thermal processing conditions applied. Thus, the present model can assist in the design and analysis of these laminates to tailor mechanical and strength characteristics. The optimization option offered by this model can therefore be of great benefit in terms of performance tailoring and weight-saving capabilities.

REFERENCES

1. R. B. Pipes and N. J. Pagano, Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates Under Uniform Axial Extension. *J. of Composite Materials*, **4**, 538-548 (1970).
2. A. S. D. Wang and F. W. Crossman, Edge Effects on Thermally Induced Stresses in Composite Laminates. *J. of Composite Materials*, **11**, 300-312 (1977).
3. E. F. Rybicki and D. W. Schmuesser, Effect of Stacking Sequence and Lay-Up Angle on Free Edge Stresses Around a Hole in a Laminated Plate Under Tension. *J. of Composite Materials*, **12**, 300-313 (1978).
4. J. D. Muzzy and A. O. Kays, Thermoplastic vs. Thermosetting Structural Composites. *Polymer Composites*, **5** (3), 169-172 (1984).
5. J. A. Nairn and P. Zoller, The Development of Residual Thermal Stresses in Amorphous and Semicrystalline Thermoplastic Matrix Composites. *Toughened Composites, ASTM STP 937*, Philadelphia, PA, 328-341 (1987).
6. G. Jeronimidis and A. T. Parkyn, Residual Stresses in Carbon Fibre-Thermoplastic Matrix Laminates. *J. of Composite Materials*, **12** (5), 401-415 (1988).
7. K. S. Kim, H. T. Hahn and R. B. Croman, The Effect of Cooling Rate on Residual Stress in a Thermoplastic Composite. *J. of Composite Technology and Research*, **11** (2), 47-52 (1989).
8. W. J. Unger and J. S. Hansen, The Effect of Cooling Rate and Annealing on Residual Stress Development in Graphite Fibre Reinforced PEEK Laminates. *J. of Composite Materials*, **27** (2), 108-137 (1993).
9. T. J. Chapman, J. W. Gillespie Jr., R. B. Pipes, J.-A. E. Manson and J. C. Seferis, Prediction of Process-Induced Residual Stresses in Thermoplastic Composites. *J. of Composite Materials*, **24** (6), 616-643 (1990).
10. W. E. Lawrence, J.-A. E. Manson, J. C. Seferis, J. W. Gillespie Jr. and R. B. Pipes, Prediction of Residual Stress in Continuous Fiber Semicrystalline Thermoplastic Composites: A Kinetic-Viscoelastic Approach. *5th ASC Technical Conf.*, East Lansing, MI, 401-414 (June 1990).
11. D. J. Blundell, J. M. Chalmers, M. W. Mackenzie, and W. F. Gaskin, Crystalline Morphology of the Matrix of PEEK-Carbon Fiber Aromatic Polymer Composites. 1 - Assessment of Crystallinity. *SAMPE Quarterly*, **16** (4), 22-30 (1985).
12. D. J. Blundell and B. N. Osborn, The Morphology of Poly-(aryl-ether-ether-ketone). *Polymer*, **24**, 953-958 (1983).
13. D. J. Blundell and B. N. Osborn, Crystalline Morphology of the Matrix of PEEK-Carbon Fiber Aromatic Polymer Composites. 2 - Crystallization Behavior. *SAMPE Quarterly*, **17** (1), 1-6 (1985).
14. C. N. Velisaris and J. C. Seferis, Crystallization Kinetics of Polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) Matrices. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **26** (22), 1574-1581 (1986).
15. M. M. Domb, Analysis of Thermal Residual Stresses During Processing of Fibre-Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites. Ph. D. Thesis, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Toronto, (1995).

Figure 1. Two-Dimensional Space Domain of the Problem.

Figure 2. Solution Procedure for the Incremental Residual Stress Analysis of a Thermoplastic Composite Laminate During Processing.

Figure 3. Cooling Rate Effect on the Interlaminar Normal Stress σ_z at the 0/90 Interface of a $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ APC-2 Laminate Cooled from the Molten State.

Figure 4. Cooling Rate Effect on the Interlaminar Shear Stress τ_{yz} at the 0/90 Interface of a $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ APC-2 Laminate Cooled from the Molten State.

